

Synthesis report on initialization and ensemble generation

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1. Executive summary

Météo-France is releasing the next generation of its seasonal forecasting system called System 9, based on the coupled climate model CNRM-CM (Voltaire et al, 2019). While the modeling options for System 9 are described in the companion deliverable D3.1.2 of the present C3S2_370_MF contract (Recommendations for the System 9 model, Specq et al., 2024), this report describes the choices relative to the seasonal forecasting setup that is applied to the climate model, justified by comparisons between several options. The focus is set on the ensemble generation methodology and on the initial conditions. The setup is defined as follows:

- The ensemble size is 31 for the reforecasts, and 51 for the real-time forecasts.
- Ensemble members are generated with:
 - A lagged initialization procedure, where ensemble members are initialized from 3 different start dates (i.e forecast batches) before or on the first day of each month.
 - Online perturbations of the atmosphere dynamics using the Stochastic Dynamics approach (Batté and Déqué, 2016).
- Initial conditions come from:
 - The ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al, 2020) for the atmosphere and land surface.
 - An in-house ocean-only simulation for ocean and sea-ice, that is forced at the surface by atmospheric fluxes from ERA5 and nudged towards the GLORYS12V1 ocean reanalysis in temperature and salinity.

2. Introduction

The current Météo-France seasonal forecasting system 8 (Batté et al, 2021) is based on the CNRM-CM coupled climate model (Voltaire et al, 2019). In order to issue seasonal forecasts on a monthly basis, this model is provided with realistic initial conditions. Moreover, the production of ensemble forecasts from the initialized CNRM-CM model requires an ensemble generation approach. System 8 ensemble generation is based on a two-tier methodology involving a lagged initialization procedure and in-run perturbation of the atmospheric dynamics of each member with the procedure called Stochastic Dynamics (Batté and Déqué, 2016).

The new version of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting system is based on an updated version of CNRM-CM, described in a companion deliverable (D3.2.1, Recommendations for the System 9 model, Specq et al., 2024). This release is the opportunity to adjust, if needed, the initialization and ensemble generation methodologies that were used in System 8. For this reason, several scientific questions were raised in an interim report (D3.1.1, Interim reports on coupled model development, Guérémy et al., 2023) :

- Is the use of Stochastic Dynamics still relevant for ensemble generation with the new model version, compared to a simpler initial perturbation method?
- What is the optimal dispatch of the ensemble members across forecast batches in the lagged initialization procedure?
- What is the most relevant method to generate initial conditions, between a coupled run (as used in System 8) or a separate initialization of each model component?

This report describes the investigations to address these questions. Section 3 indicates the retained ensemble sizes based on previous work from Work Package 4 of the present contract, and Section 4 focuses on the ensemble generation methodology. Section 5 is dedicated to the selected methodology for initialization and Section 6 provides a recap of the System 9 seasonal forecasting setup.

3. Ensemble size

The real-time ensemble size for System 9 is chosen to remain 51 members, as in System 8. This ensemble size is a good compromise between maintaining a good balance in the C3S multi-system, and keeping constraints on operational supervision and computing costs at a reasonable level. However, System 9 is slightly cheaper than System 8 in terms of computing cost, by about 20%. This makes it possible to increase reforecast ensemble size.

In Work Package 4 of the present C3S2_370_MF contract, Task 4.2 investigates the benefits of increasing reforecast ensemble size compared to the current 25 members used in the System 8 reforecasts. The main conclusion of Task 4.2 (Deliverable D4.2.1, Specq et al., 2023) is that 25 members are broadly sufficient for the main uses of an operational seasonal reforecast, i.e sampling the model climatology, correcting biases and verifying forecast quality. We therefore decide to keep a similar ensemble size for System 9 reforecasts. We only increase it from 25 to 31 members to take advantage of the small gain in computing cost.

4. Ensemble generation

4.1 Two ensemble perturbation methods

Twin reforecast experiments have been carried out, differing only by the perturbation methodology generating the forecast members : stochastic dynamics on the one hand, and initial perturbations on the other hand. They are meant to address a scientific question raised in Section 6.4 of the interim report D3.1.1, which suggested that initial perturbations could lead to better forecasts than stochastic dynamics.

Stochastic dynamics is a methodology of online perturbation of the atmosphere dynamics that consists in randomly adding past errors of the atmosphere model in the course of the simulation. The sequences of errors, sampled on a daily basis, are randomly taken from a pool of previously estimated errors using the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al 2020) as a reference. Then, for a given set of initial conditions, each member is entirely defined by the sequence of daily error corrections from the start to the end of the simulation. Details on the stochastic dynamics method are provided in Batté and Déqué (2016), while the various options for the present experiment (e.g how to define the pool of perturbations) are the same as System 8 and can be found in the System 8 technical documentation (Batté et al, 2021).

As for the initial perturbation methodology, it uses the same set of error corrections as stochastic dynamics, but a correction field is only added to the atmosphere initial conditions while the model is allowed to evolve freely afterward. Then, for a given set of initial conditions, each member is entirely defined by the random error added to the model at time step 0.

Apart from the ensemble generation methodology, the two reforecast experiments are the same and have the following characteristics:

- The modeling options are those of System 9, as described in Deliverable D3.1.2.
- Initialization is made separately for each model component, following the “standard” initialization (Option 3) described in Section 5 below. In particular, atmosphere initial conditions directly come from the ERA5 reanalysis.
- Reforecasts are initialized using the 1 May and 1 November initial conditions between 1995 and 2018. There is no lagged initialization at this stage to isolate the effect of the perturbation methodology. Years 1993 and 1994 have been excluded due to a temporary inconsistency in the ocean initial conditions.
- Reforecast experiments have 15 ensemble members.

4.2 Stochastic dynamics or initial perturbations?

Figure 1 provides a comparison of biases in geopotential height at 500 hPa (Z500) of the two reforecast experiments described above during the JJA and DJF seasons. Although the structure of the biases is similar in both experiments and reflects the behavior of System 9 modeling options, the stochastic dynamics experiment has lower biases compared to initial perturbations, as shown by the mean absolute bias values above each panel. This is especially true in the mid-latitudes, and such a reduction of biases is an expected impact of stochastic dynamics (Batté and Déqué, 2016). A similar comparison also shows slightly lower precipitation biases for stochastic dynamics, and similar near-surface temperature biases for both methods (not shown).

Stochastic dynamics also leads to lower SST biases, especially after the May initialization. This is particularly noticeable in the Niño3.4 region as illustrated in Figure 2, but is also appears on the mean absolute biases at the global scale (not shown). The first panel of Figure 2 highlights the benefit of stochastic dynamics in reducing the strong positive drift of System 9 after the May initialization, a flaw that was already raised in the companion deliverable D3.1.2 (see Figure 4, left panel, “P6+” curve).

Figure 1: Z500 biases (in m) in System 9 with an ensemble based on stochastic dynamics (left column) or initial perturbations (right column), over the 1995-2018 reforecast period. Upper row: JJA bias (init. May). Lower row: DJF bias (init. November). The global mean absolute bias is indicated in the title of each panel. Reference: ERA5.

Figure 2: Mean bias (in K) of the Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature in the System 8 reforecasts (cyan), the System 9 stochastic dynamics ensemble (blue) and the System 9 initial perturbations ensemble (red), over the 1995-2018 period. Left panel: May initialization. Right panel: November initialization. Reference: ERA5.

When it comes to forecast skill, we use the meanACC score over several spatial domains in order to get an overview of the predictive ability in each reforecast. The domains and variables of interest are the same as in D3.1.2, and are indicated in Figure 3. The uncertainty of the scores related to the years in the sample is assessed through a bootstrap with each score computed 1,000 times from 24 random years drawn with replacement in the 1995-2018 period. The solid bars indicate the median of the bootstrap and the error bars indicate the 5%-95% confidence interval. The bootstrap is also used for significance testing of the differences between two scores, which have to be strictly positive or negative at the 95% level. Significant differences are shown with triangles, where an upward-pointing (resp. downward-pointing) triangle above a bar means that the score indicated by this bar is significantly higher (resp. lower) than the score in the neighboring bar which has the same color as the triangle. Figure 3 shows six cases with a significant difference between stochastic dynamics and initial perturbations, four of which corresponding to better forecasts with stochastic dynamics. Moreover, the stochastic dynamics experiment often outperforms System 8, which is not the case of the initial perturbations experiment.

A similar comparison, provided in Figure 4, is made on correlation of monthly Niño3.4 sea surface temperature reforecasts. The most notable fact is that both experiments significantly outperform System 8 over the first months of forecast. Moreover, reforecasts with initial perturbations outperform those with stochastic dynamics at lead times of 3 and 4 months after the May initialization (July and August).

The overall result of the comparison in Figures 1 to 4 is that both ensemble generation methodologies are fit for purpose and that the differences in terms of forecast quality are small. Additional investigation has also shown there is no drastic difference in ensemble spread between both methods (not shown). However, we claim that stochastic dynamics is a preferable choice for the following reasons:

- It leads to lower biases than initial perturbations.
- For the selected forecast scores, it outperforms System 8 more often than initial perturbations does (10 times against 7 times)

System 9 ensemble members will therefore be generated with the stochastic dynamics methodology, as in System 8.

Figure 3: meanACC scores of the System 8 reforecasts (cyan), the System 9 stochastic dynamics experiment (blue) and the System 9 initial perturbations experiment (red), over the 1995-2018 period and various spatial domains. The error bars indicate the 5%-95% confidence interval of each score, estimated through a bootstrap over the reforecast years (1,000 draws with replace of the years from 1993 to 2018). See text for details on the upward and downward-pointing triangles. References: ERA5 (T2m, Z500) and MSWEP (precipitation).

Figure 4: Temporal correlation of the Niño3.4 monthly mean sea surface temperature reforecasts of System 8 (cyan), System 9 with stochastic dynamics (blue) and System 9 with initial perturbations (red), in the six months after the May (left panel) and November (right panel) initializations. Significant differences are estimated through a bootstrap procedure and indicated with triangles as in Figure 5 (see text for details). Reference: ERA5.

4.3 What is the optimal lagged optimization scheme?

Beyond online perturbation of the model runs with stochastic dynamics, System 8 is operated with a lagged initialization procedure. Ensemble members are generated in successive forecast batches with different sets of initial conditions, described in the System 8 technical documentation (Batté et al, 2021). The current sets of initial conditions are :

- The 1st of each month M (reference forecast start date) for Batch 3
- The preceding Thursday in month M-1 for Batch 2
- The second preceding Thursday in month M-1 for Batch 1

The numbering of the batches reflects the chronological order of forecast production. Table 1 provides the number of members produced in each batch.

	Batch 1 (Month M-1, 2nd-to-last Thursday)	Batch 2 (Month M-1, Last Thursday)	Batch 3 (Month M, 1st day)	Total ensemble size
Reforecast	12	12	1	25
Real-time	25	25	1	51

Table 1: Distribution of ensemble members across forecast batches in the Météo-France System 8 lagged initialization procedure

This lagged initialization is designed to better account for uncertainties in the initial conditions, but also to cope with operational constraints, as it avoids the simultaneous real-time production of 51

members that is more challenging to manage. However, it has been suggested in the interim report D3.1.1 that another distribution of the members among the forecast batches, giving more weights to the most recent dates, might lead to higher forecast skill (see D3.1.1, Section 6.3).

This is further investigated in the present section with a large pool of already available System 8-like ensemble members. These members come from:

- the official System 8 reforecast
- the System 8 reforecast extension produced in Task 1.3 of the present contract (additional members produced for the May and November initializations)
- an 11-member “burst” reforecast experiment with System 8 model and setup, starting on 1 May and 1 November

All this data covers the 1993-2018 period. Table 2 summarizes the available reforecast members, while Table 3 indicates the 7 investigated options for lagged initialization, described as proportions of members coming from each batch.

	Batch 1 (Month M-1 2nd-to-last Thursday)	Batch 2 (Month M-1, Last Thursday)	Batch 3 (Month M, 1st day)
Available members (May and Nov, 1993-2018)	25	25	11

Table 2: Available System 8 members for random draws across forecast batches in the May and November initializations of the 1993-2018 period.

The comparison between these options is made on the basis of 31-member ensembles, which is the official System 9 reforecast size (see Section 3). The 31 members are drawn from the three batches according to the proportions in Table 3. For instance, Option 3 is evaluated by drawing 12 members out 25 from Batch 1 (0.4 x 31), 15 members out of 25 from Batch 2 (0.5 x 31), and 3 members out of 11 from Batch 3 (0.1 x 31). The process is repeated 1,000 times to estimate the uncertainty related to the random draws.

Figure 5 shows a selection of meanACC scores obtained with each option, for both the first monthly lead times and a key target seasonal mean (e.g DJF for November initialization). The variables under consideration are Z500 and near-surface temperature (T2m) over the specified domains. The number of members drawn from each batch, according to the proportions in Table 2, is indicated in the legend.

	Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 3	Remarks
Option 1	0.5	0.5	0*	Same distribution as System 8
Option 2	0.4	0.6	0*	
Option 3	0.4	0.5	0.1	Minimal increase of Batch 3 weight
Option 4	0.4	0.4	0.2	
Option 5	0.33	0.33	0.33	Evenly distributed members
Option 6	0.2	0.6	0.2	
Option 7	0	0.8	0.2	No Batch 1

Table 3: Proportion of ensemble members across forecast batches in the 7 tested options. *The ensemble size of Batch 3 in Options 1 and 2 is not strictly 0 because at least one member is used so as to have a control run from the latest available initial conditions.

The key result from Figure 5 is that the distribution of members across batches has little impact on forecast skill from the second month onwards, and especially on the forecast months 2-4 seasonal mean. The only notable difference is in the first forecast month, for which the highest forecast performance is achieved when members are evenly distributed among batches (Option 5). In this first month, meanACC unsurprisingly tends to increase as the weight given to Batch 1 — which has the largest lag — decreases. As for ensemble spread, additional investigation on the spread-error ratio of the forecasts (not shown) has revealed there is no systematic advantage to one option in the first forecast month, and no drastic difference between all of them beyond.

Judging by Figure 5, Option 5 is theoretically the best distribution across forecast batches given its performance for month 1. Nevertheless, in a real-time context, it would require the production of 17 Batch 3 members initialized on the 1st of each month ($0.33 \times 51 = 17$). This creates a risk of occasional failure in operational delivery targets. We do not intend to take that risk for month 1, which is not the key target of a seasonal forecasting system. Given that the difference between all options is minimal after the first month, we eventually consider our lagged initialization is not worth changing. The retained option is Option 1: it is the same as System 8, and described in Table 1.

Figure 5: meanACC scores for various distributions of System 8 forecast members across forecast batches. The variable of interest, spatial domain and initialization are indicated in the title of each panel. The scores refer to the monthly lead times 1 to 4 and the three-month seasonal mean of a key target season (to the right). The error bars indicate the 5%-95% confidence interval of each score, estimated through 1,000 draws of members among the pool described in Table 2. Reference: ERA5 (T2m, Z500).

5. Initial conditions for seasonal forecasts

A crucial issue for initialization of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting systems is the absence of a dedicated data assimilation for CNRM-CM. This leads to rely on data assimilation performed by

other institutions in reanalyses and real-time analyses, and to make the data compatible with the CNRM-CM modeling options.

The current initialization procedure for System 8 is mostly based on a preliminary simulation using the same coupled model as for the forecast, that is nudged towards reanalysis data and runs continuously to output initial conditions at regular time intervals. This procedure enables to have initial condition files that are:

- Ready to use in forecast mode, because they are produced by the same model.
- Consistent across the components of the coupled model to reduce the initialization shock.
- Representative of the real-world thanks to nudging.

In this preliminary simulation, both the atmosphere and the liquid ocean are nudged. The Arpege-Climat atmosphere model is tightly nudged towards the ERA5 reanalysis with a 6-hour time scale, while the NEMO ocean model is nudged in temperature and salinity towards the GLORYS12V1 ocean reanalysis from the Copernicus Marine Services, with a time scale of 2 days. This coupled-nudged simulation is denoted CPLI (CouPLed Initialization). More details can be found in System 8 documentation (Batté et al 2021, Section 3).

An alternative option is to initialize each model component separately, as in the former version of the Météo-France forecasting System 7 (see Batté et al 2019, Section 4). In this procedure, atmosphere and land surface initial conditions directly come from the ERA5 reanalysis. As for ocean and sea-ice initial conditions, they are provided by another preliminary simulation where the ocean and sea-ice models are running together with no coupling to the atmosphere, while being forced at the surface by ERA5 fluxes and nudged in the liquid ocean towards GLORYS12V1. This forced-nudged ocean simulation is denoted STDI (STanDard Initialization). The oceanic nudging is similar to that of the CPLI run.

While both approaches have been reasonably satisfactory for initialization of the atmosphere and the ocean in the previous systems, the initialization of sea-ice is a challenging task because there is no sea-ice reference data that can be made compatible with sea-ice modeling in CNRM-CM. Consequently, in both CPLI and STDI simulations, there is no constraint from real-world sea-ice to generate sea-ice initial conditions. This leads to unrealistically low sea-ice quantities in the CPLI simulation designed to initialize System 8, that might lead to a complete melting during the summer season in forecasting mode. To solve this problem, initialization of sea-ice in System 8 does not come from the CPLI run but from an independent STDI run using the same ocean and sea-ice model. This is possible because STDI provides more realistic sea-ice, in spite of the absence of constraints as well. The main characteristics of the initialization procedures for System 7 and System 8 are summarized in Table 4.

The options under consideration for the initialization of System 9 build on these previously implemented approaches:

- Option 1: Relying exclusively on a coupled-nudged run CPLI, including for sea-ice
- Option 2: Using a hybrid approach as in System 8 (STDI for sea-ice, CPLI for the rest)
- Option 3: Using ERA5 (for the atmosphere and land surface) and a forced-nudged ocean run STDI (for ocean and sea-ice), as in System 7

	System 7	System 8
Atmosphere	ERA5	In-house coupled-nudged run (CPLI)
Ocean (liquid)	In-house forced-nudged ocean run (STDI)	In-house coupled-nudged run (CPLI)
Sea-ice	In-house forced-nudged ocean run (STDI)	In-house forced-nudged ocean run (STDI)
Land surface	ERA5	In-house coupled-nudged run (CPLI)

Table 4: Data sources for the initialization of the CNRM-CM coupled model components in Météo-France seasonal forecasting Systems 7 and 8.

Given the above-mentioned issue on sea-ice initialization, the choice between the three options is addressed by comparing the sea-ice initial conditions in both STDI and CPLI simulations when the new modeling options of System 9 are implemented (i.e NEMO 4.2 and SI³, see Deliverable 3.1.2 for details). Figure 6 shows this comparison on Arctic sea-ice thickness over the first five years of the reforecast period, from January 1993 to December 1997. The key point is the difference between the solid red and cyan curves, and how they compare to PIOMAS reference data. It is clear from Figure 6 that STDI produces far more realistic Arctic sea-ice than CPLI: this is the same issue as in System 8, that led to differentiate sea-ice initialization from the rest. As a reminder, the previously used STDI sea-ice initial conditions from System 8 are also shown with the dashed red curve: its comparison with the new STDI run in the solid red curve additionally demonstrates the added value of the ocean and sea-ice model updates of System 9.

Consequently, the initialization of System 9 is chosen to follow the above-listed Option 3, similar to System 7 and described in the first column of Table 4. The arguments are as follows:

- STDI produces realistic sea-ice initial conditions while CPLI does not (Figure 6): this prevents from using CPLI for sea-ice initialization and excludes Option 1.
- Option 2 could be used as in System 8, but requires to monitor two preliminary simulations (CPLI and STDI) instead of one for Option 3 (STDI only). This is less convenient in a real-time operational context.
- Additional investigation (not shown) has demonstrated that Option 2 leads to lower atmospheric forecast skill than Option 3 in the subseasonal time scales (up to week 6). This is not crucial to seasonal forecast skill, but will be for the next CNRM contribution to the Subseasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) database, based on the System 9 setup.

Figure 6: Monthly sea-ice thickness (in m) averaged over the Arctic region (latitude > 60°N) from January 1993 to December 1997, in the PIOMAS reference data (solid black) and in several in-house simulations providing the sea-ice initial conditions for seasonal forecasts. Dashed red: forced-nudged simulation STDI using System 8 ocean and sea-ice models. Solid red: forced-nudged simulation STDI using System 9 ocean and sea-ice models. Solid cyan: coupled-nudged simulation CPLI using the System 9 coupled model.

6. Conclusion

The seasonal forecasting setup for System 9 is summarized and compared to that of System 8 in the following Table 5. Differences are indicated in bold red. The main methodological difference between System 8 and 9 is the change in the initialization procedure, while the ensemble generation approach is similar except for a slight change in reforecast ensemble size. Note that even for unchanged methods, the underlying data (e.g stochastic dynamics perturbations, sea-ice initial conditions) is obviously changed because it is computed with the new modeling options of System 9 described in the companion Deliverable D3.1.2.

		System 8	System 9
Ensemble perturbation		Stochastic dynamics	Stochastic dynamics
Lagged initialization	Reforecast size Batch 1	12	15
	Reforecast size Batch 2	12	15
	Reforecast size Batch 3	1	1
	Real-time size Batch 1	25	25
	Real-time size Batch 2	25	25
	Real-time size Batch 3	1	1
Atmosphere initialization		In-house coupled-nudged run	ERA5
Ocean initialization		In-house coupled-nudged run	In-house forced-nudged ocean run
Sea-ice initialization		In-house forced-nudged ocean run	In-house forced-nudged ocean run
Land surface initialization		In-house coupled-nudged run	ERA5

Table 5: Comparison between the ensemble generation and initialization procedures of the current Météo-France System 8 and the new System 9 seasonal forecasting systems. Differences are shown in bold red.

7. References

Batté, L., and M. Déqué (2016). Randomly correcting model errors in the ARPEGE-Climate v6.1 component of CNRM-CM: applications for seasonal forecasts. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9, 2055-2076.

Batté, L., L. Dorel, C. Ardilouze and J-F. Guérémy (2019). Documentation of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 7. Deliverable D3.1.1 of C3S_330_MF contract. <https://www.umr-cnrm.fr/IMG/pdf/system7-technical.pdf>

Batté, L., L. Dorel, C. Ardilouze and J-F. Guérémy (2021). Documentation of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 8. Deliverable D3.3.1 of C3S_330_MF contract. <http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/IMG/pdf/system8-technical.pdf>

Guérémy, J-F., C. Ardilouze, L. Batté, J. Beuvier, L. Dorel, D. Specq, F. Thottuvilampil Shahul Hameed (2023). Interim report of coupled model developments. Deliverable D3.1.1 of C3S2_370_MF contract.

Hersbach, H., et al., 2020: The ERA5 global reanalysis, *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146 (730), 1999-2049.

Specq, D., S. Li and L. Batté (2023). Benefits of increasing reforecast ensemble size. Deliverable D4.2.1 of C3S2_370_MF contract.

Specq, D., J. Beuvier, F. Thottuvilampil Shahul Hameed, L. Dorel, C. Ardilouze, L. Batté (2024). Recommendations for the System 9 model. Deliverable 3.1.2 of C3S2_370_MF contract.

Voldoire, A., D. Saint-Martin, S. Senesi, B. Decharme, A. Alias, M. Chevallier et al (2019). Evaluation of CMIP6 DECK experiments with CNRM-CM6-1. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 11.

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